

FORTRESS STADIUM: A CASE STUDY

Session 2020-2024

SUPERVISOR
Dr. FARYAL ABDULLAH

SUBMITTED BY
MASHAL – ULLAH

DEPARTMENT OF INTERIOR DESIGN
UNIVERSITY OF HOME ECONOMICS

FORTRESS STADIUM: A CASE STUDY

A research work submitted to University of Home Economics in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor's in Interior Design

SUBMITTED BY

MASHAL – ULLAH

SESSION 2020-2024

DEPARTMENT OF INTERIOR DESIGN

UNIVERSITY OF HOME ECONOMICS GULBERG, LAHORE

RESEARCH COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

This is to clarify the research work described in this thesis submitted by Ms. Mashal Ullah to Department of Interior Design, has been carried out under my direct Supervision. I have personally gone through the raw data and certify the correctness and authenticity of the results reported herein. I further certify that thesis data has not been used in parts or full, in a manuscript already submitted or in the process of submission in partial fulfilment of the award of any other degree from any other institution or home or abroad. I also certify that the enclosed manuscript has been prepared under my supervision and I endorse its evaluation for the award of BS degree through the official procedure of university.

Supervisor

Dr. Faryal Abdullah

University of Home Economics

Date:

DECLARATION

I, **Mashal Ullah Roll No.29** session 2020-2024 solemnly declare that the work submitted in this thesis entitled “Fortress Stadium: A Case Study” is my own and has not been presented to any other institution or university of the degree. The work has not been plagiarized. It is an original work. This work has been completed at the UHE.

Mashal Ullah

Researcher,

Department of Interior Design.

DEDICATION

This study is wholeheartedly dedicated to my respected supervisor Dr. Faryal Abdullah for providing guidance and support through challenges for her supervision and her knowledge in field of research that remarkably helped me to complete my study.

This study is wholeheartedly dedicated to my beloved parents for their inspiration, advices and persistence support and encouragement, who continually provide their moral, spiritual, emotional and financial support.

Furthermore, I would like to dedicate my study to my mother's brother and my beloved Uncle Muhammad Ali Butt for his support and for helping me find accurate research material for this study without which my research would be incomplete.

ACKNOELEGEMENT

In the name of Allah, the most merciful and benevolent.

First, I would humbly thank Allah Almighty for giving me the strength and the capabilities to write my thesis. Without His blessings, I would not have been able to go through my work.

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Mashal Ullah

ABSTRACT

Fortress Stadium, located in the heart of Lahore, Cantt, stands as significant architectural and cultural landmark. This thesis presents a case study of the Fortress stadium, exploring its architectural significance, exterior and interior analysis. Build in the mid-20th century; Fortress Stadium reflects a fusion of traditional design and modern design principles, blending elements of contemporary form. The stadium's distinctive use of arches, ornamentation and open spaces displays a respect for local aesthetics while meeting the functional needs of multi-purpose recreational facilities. The study investigates the interior layout of Fortress Stadium, which is designed in a way to accommodate large crowd for a variety of events, ranging from sports competition to cultural festivals. The open-air structure complemented by strategically placed seating arrangements and open concourses that facilitate crowd movement and offer panoramic views of the event. Its interior design reflects a minimalistic approach, prioritizing functionalities and space utilization over ornamental excess, making it an efficient public space. Through qualitative research method including archival research, site visits and interview with key administrative person, this thesis delves into the architectural evolution of Fortress Stadium and its role as social and cultural hub. The study also highlights the reservation efforts and challenges associated with maintaining such a historically significant structure in a rapidly urbanizing city. By positioning Fortress Stadium within the broader context of Lahore architectural heritage, this thesis aims to contribute to discourse on the architectural significant and interior layout of Fortress Stadium.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

Lahore Fortress Stadium, located in the vibrant city of Lahore, Pakistan, stands as a testament to the nation's rich history and cultural heritage. Built in the mid-20th century, this iconic structure has not only served as a premier venue for a myriad of sports events but has also hosted countless cultural and community gatherings. The stadium holds a unique place in the hearts of the people of Lahore. Also has played a significant role in shaping the social and cultural landscape of the city.

The study of Lahore Fortress Stadium is of paramount importance for several reasons. First, it provides insights into the architectural and historical evolution of one of Lahore's most significant landmarks. Understanding the design and construction of the stadium, as well as the various modifications it has undergone over the years, offers valuable perspectives on the architectural heritage of Pakistan. Second, examining the stadium's role in hosting major sporting and cultural events sheds light on its impact on the local community and economy. The stadium's influence extends beyond its physical structure, encompassing the social interactions and communal spirit fostered within its walls.

The primary objective of this thesis is to explore the multifaceted significance of Lahore Fortress Stadium through a comprehensive case study. This includes an examination of its historical development, architectural features, and its role as a venue for sports and cultural events. Additionally, the study aims to assess the stadium's social and cultural impact on the city of Lahore and identify the challenges and opportunities it faces in the contemporary era.

To achieve these objectives, qualitative methods approach employed. The methodology will involve a thorough literature review on history of stadiums, a review of Fortress Stadium,

interview with administrative authority. By triangulating data from multiple sources, this study aims to provide a holistic understanding of Lahore Fortress Stadium and its enduring legacy.

In conclusion, this thesis endeavours to contribute to the body of knowledge on sports and cultural venues in Pakistan by presenting a detailed case study of Lahore Fortress Stadium. Through this study, it is hoped that the significance of such structures in fostering community spirit and preserving cultural heritage will be underscored, providing valuable insights for future research and policy-making.

1.1 Problem Statement

This research focuses on Fortress Stadium's historical development, architectural significance, socio-cultural impact, and the current challenges it faces. The goal is to provide insights and recommendations for preserving its heritage while enhancing its functionality and relevance in contemporary society.

1.2 Objective

- To examine the historical evolution of Lahore fortress stadium, including its origin contraction and development of its purpose and usage over time
- To analyse the architectural design and feature of Lahore stadium exploring its significance in relation to historical and cultural context of Lahore
- To investigate the role of avenue for sport events, cultural activities and community gathering and its impact on local community and economy
- To provide insight and personal recommendation for future management and utilization of Lahore fortress stadium.

1.3 Significance of study

This study is significant as it sheds light on Lahore Fortress Stadium's rich historical, cultural, and architectural heritage. By exploring its evolution, role in hosting major events and impact on the local community, the research underscores the stadium's importance as a cultural landmark. Additionally, the study addresses current challenges and proposes recommendations for preserving its heritage while enhancing its functionality. The insights gained will contribute to a deeper understanding of how such structures can influence urban development, community identity, and cultural preservation, offering valuable guidance for policymakers and urban planners.

1.4 Scope and limitation

This study aims to show comprehensively examine Lahore Fortress Stadium, focusing on its historical development, architectural significance, and its role in hosting sports and cultural events. By employing a qualitative research method approach that includes literature reviews, interviews, the research seeks to understand the stadium's impact on the local community and economy. However, the study faces limitations such as restricted access to historical records, geographic constraints to Lahore, and time constraints affecting data collection and analysis. Additionally, any ongoing renovations during the study period may influence the findings' relevance.

CHAPTER 2

Literature Review

This chapter throws light upon a brief history of stadiums. The literature is reviewed from articles, thesis on stadiums, books, polo clubs and authorised sports websites such as Pakistan sports boards and Newspapers.

Lev Zetline writes in Britannica "*Stadium*". He defines stadium as "stadium are enclosure that combines broad space for athletic games and other exhibition with large seating capacity for spectators. The name derives from Greek unit of measure, the Stade, the distance covered in the Greek footraces (about 600 feet's). The course for the footrace in the ancient Olympic Games at Olympics was exactly a Stade in length and the word for the unit of measure become transferred first to footrace and then to the place in which the race was run."

Lev Zetline further writes "the first Greeks stadium was long and narrow, in U shape or a horseshoe. They were sometimes cut into the side of the hill, as at Thebes, Epidaurus and at Olympics."

Elio Nassar writes in his thesis "*Ice Hockey Arena Milano-Cortina 2026 Winter Olympic*" SECTION 2 under the heading "*History of sport arenas from originality to modern arenas*" in 2023. "The first stadium to be designed was built by Greeks, dating to 776 B.C. the stadium was originally designed and build so the audience could see the festivities from the slopes of Mount Cronin: nevertheless, it was gradually shifted eastward until it was finally put outside Zeus temple."

"Blame the Greeks for the horseshoe-style stadium and the Romes for all those high rising cheap seats. But at least those two cultures gave us early stadium design, something we

lacked for centuries upon centuries until the 1800s rolled around” says Tim Newcomb in his article “*Embracing the horseshoe: A look through centuries of stadium design*”.

Tim Newcomb further says “while the Greek gives us stadiums in the half-dozen or so centuries before Christ, credit the Romans for really giving stadiums a monumental shift in the first few centuries after.”

“The Colosseum, built in 80 AD, still serves as the father of all modern stadiums.” Tim Cahill, Architect of the NFL’s newest venue, Levi’s Stadium in Santa Clara, California, tells SI.com his design was modelled after a “Roman amphitheatre”. The Figure 1 below is of Colosseum in Rome.

Figure 1 Colosseum in Rome

(Source: Don Kitwood/Getty Images)

Joshua Kagavi writes in his article “*5 Extraordinary Ancient Stadium that Influenced Future Arenas*”. The mystical site of Delphi, situated amidst a gorgeous mountain range, was the omphalos, or hub of ancient Greek culture and centered around the cult of Apollo and mysterious oracle. The stadium of Delphi held footraces as part of the Pythian Games and unlike the older and more prestigious Olympics, women were allowed to compete in some events. The **Error! Reference source not found.** below is of Stadium of Delphi.

Figure 2 Women and men competed in foot races at the ancient Stadium of Delphi.

(Source: Federica Grassi/Getty Image)

Beth Karikari says in “*Sports Stadiums Past and Present*” from high school sports to global Olympic games, sports stadium plays a big role in our lives. Sports stadiums often push the frontiers of architectural ingenuity, symbols of pride and achievement for their communities. They owe so much to their ancient predecessors. Indeed, it is fascinating how the sports stadium has evolved over time and how much it has also stayed true to its ancient roots.

written in one of article of Webuild S.p.A. “*From the Colosseum to the World Cup: the evolution of Stadiums throughout history*”. After the fall of the Roman Empire, nearly two millennia passed before stadium experienced a revival driven by the return of Olympic Games in 1896. The stadium for the first modern Olympics in Athens, considered the father of modern stadiums, was reconstruction of one originally built by Herodes Attious. This followed by the White City Stadium in 1906, which could hold 150,000 spectators and boasted the first covered grandstand in history.

“Our requirements in what makes a great stadium experience have radically changed. Stadium have to continually adjust and innovated to deliver” says Jan Kee Mon while giving interview to Sport Tomorrow when the interviewer asked what have changes in stadium from past to present.

Stadium design has evolved significantly. According to Guttman (1992) in "*the Olympics: A history of modern game, modern*" modern stadium began to take shape in the 19th century, focusing on accommodating larger audiences and diversifying the types of events held.

Stadium have always been centre for public gathering. Bale (2003) in his book "*Sports Geography*" notes that stadium provide a communal space where fans came together, sharing a collective identity tied to their favourite teams or events.

Vamplew discusses in his article "*The evolution of stadium: Sports History press*" how pre-1950s stadiums focused on maximizing seating capacity with little concern for spectator comfort or technologies amenities. In contrast, contemporary stadiums emphasize luxury seating climate control and digital enhancement.

Stadium built in 1950s, like Tokyo's National stadium, were part of post war reconstruction efforts. According to Andrews in his book "*Post-War Architecture: Stadiums*" these stadiums were simpler but reflected the optimism of time. They were built quickly, focusing on durability and function.

Unlike modern stadiums, which utilized advanced materials, 1950s stadium commonly used concrete and steel. Andrew also points out that while these materials provided structural strength, they often limited the architectural freedom seen in later stadiums.

Sheard notes in his book "*Sports architecture: Design for spectators and players*" that 1950s stadiums prioritized capacity over comfort. The audience experience was secondary to the need to house large crowds, a design philosophy that has shifted significantly in recent decades.

During late 1950s and early 1960s, stadiums also played an important cultural role, often symbolizing national pride and progress and resilience. According to Vamplew in his article

“The evolution of stadium: Sports History press” these structures represent optimism and resilience of post war era, serving as monuments to collective ambition and civic pride.

Harris in his article *“Modern architectural and innovation”* details how lightweight materials enable sweeping architectural designs that enhance both form and function. Modern stadium construction employs sweeping edge materials like advanced steel alloys and fibre-reinforced polymers for durability and aesthetic appeal.

Taylor discusses in *“Green Architecture for Sports Venues.”* Modern stadium prioritized sustainability, using recyclable materials and renewable energy sources. He further says stadiums are now built with environmental impact in mind. Often incorporating solar panels and water conservation system.

According to Harris, unlike older stadiums, today's are built around spectator experiences with amenities like cushioned seating, Wi-Fi, and interactive screen. These features make stadium attractive for various events, from sports to concerts, year-round.

CHAPTER 3

Research Methodology

3.1 Nature of Research

In this thesis, a qualitative research approach is employed to explore and analyse the existing architectural and cultural significance of Fortress Stadium in Lahore.

3.2 Sampling Design

The sampling design for this study follows a purposive sampling design, where participants are deliberately selected based on their expertise, experience, and relevance to the research objectives. This non-probability sampling method ensures that the study gathers rich, detailed data from individuals who can provide meaningful insights into the architectural and cultural aspects of Fortress Stadium in Lahore.

3.3 Time Duration

The time duration for this study is planned to span approximately 6 months. This period includes time for initial literature review, data collection through interviews, observations, and archival research, followed by data analysis and the final compilation of findings.

3.4 Data Collection Procedures

Primary data collection procedures are photography, interview.

Secondary data collection procedures are textbooks, documentaries, news articles and newspapers, interviews, thesis of different researchers.

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques

The data was analysed descriptively.

CHAPTER 4

Fortress Stadium

4.1 History of Fortress Stadium, Lahore

Department of Fortress was planned and executed on late 1950s. Since 1961, Military functions, National Horse, and Cattle Shows continued to held in Fortress Stadium. Field Marshal Ayub Khan the President of Pakistan at that time, concurred the formal decision regarding reconstruction of Fortress Stadium in 1963.

Nasreddin Murat Khan a Pak-Russian architect is given credited to build Fortress Stadium. In a digital documentary of Google Art and Culture on Naserddin Murat Khan under the heading "*The Legacy of Naserddin Murat Khan*" it is stated that Naserddin have built Fortress Stadium. Not only on Google Art and Culture but also in The Friday Times article under the name "*The man who built Minar-e-Pakistan*" it is typed that Naserddin Murat Khan has given credited to build Fortress Stadium along with Qaddafi Stadium and Power Development Authority (WAPDA). Fortress Stadium was inaugurated by Gen Muhammad Azam Khan in 1960.

Nevertheless, there are no original documents found that contain the information regarding the establishment of Fortress Stadium. Furthermore, in few articles of Dawn news, and Encyclopaedia Britannica, claims that reports of government documents were either destroyed or altered. This occurred particularly around controversial issues like political records, intelligence reports, and documents related to military operations during the rule of Zia Ul Haq. The regime sought to consolidate power, eliminate political opposition, and shape the historical narrative. (Dawn, HOW ZIA RULED, 2017) (Asif, 2028) (Britannica, 2024)

Due to certain and further requirement the Fortress Stadium was reconstruction started in 1968 and completed in 1971. The main purpose of Fortress Stadium was to serve as polo ground for polo activities. It was primarily intended for military parades and sports events. Later in 1961 and up to now it is a centre of entertainment and sports hub held in Lahore, reflecting the city's growing urbanizations and modernizations effort during the period.

The Fortress Stadium started the National Horse and Cattle Show in 1962 as a hunting show at the Race Course Club Ground in Lahore. In the past, royalty, foreign heads of state, international celebrities and distinguished guests from around the world, has attended the grand spectacle.

Since 1960s, Her Majesty Queen Elizabeth of Great Britain, Duke of Edinburgh, Jacqueline Kennedy, Shah and Empress Farah Deeba of Iran, President of Turkey, King Hussain and Crown Prince Hussein bin Talal of Jordan and King Khalid and Crown Prince Fahad of Saudi Arabia have attended this that mega-festival, according to the LG and CD department report.

According to the Dawn News, Express Tribune, Daily Times and Friday Times Fortress Stadium has hosted, horse and cattle show, animal competitions, greyhound races, camping, free fall of paratroopers, bull cavalcade, passing of provincial players and industrial exhibition. Other sports and cultural activities include Football, Hockey, Kabaddi, Wrestling, Volleyball, Rope of War, Cyclist Torch Relay, Calisthenic Show, Unity Show, Picture Book Exhibition, and Classical Music. Furthermore, all Pakistan Mushaira, Book Fair, Classical Folk Music and Music, Food-Street, Pakistan Culture Street, Children's Amusement Park and flower show, laser show, agricultural, livestock, social and industrial shows, military motorcycle ride, military band, marching past, night tent pitching, gymnastics and dog and peace show, horse jumping show and luddy party.

According to a report in 2022 of Dawn News under the title “Arrangements for Lahore’s mage show in work”, the Punjab government has allocated Rs. 677,790 crores for these events. Up to 16 commissions were formulated to organize the show. The event takes place in the morning and evening.

The Fortress Stadium is now developed a popular large area of open space consisting of shopping centres, restaurants, cafés and entertainment areas and a sports stadium. It is located in Lahore Cantt, Lahore, Pakistan. Among the likes of M. M. Alam Road and Liberty Market in Gulberg, this area is a popular locale for the urban youth in Lahore. Fortress Stadium is also one of the busiest commercial areas of the city. The Chairman and Management of Fortress Stadium are serving and retired army officers. Brigadier Sikandar Khan was the Chairman Fortress Stadium (Lahore) from 2012 to 2013.

4.2 Sport Events Held in Fortress Stadium

Lahore Fortress Stadium has been the stage for numerous high-profile sporting events, most notably Horse and Cattle Show that have garnered both national and international attention. The stadium played a pivotal role during the 1961 Horse and Cattle show. It may be noted that Horse and Cattle Shows are also organized at local or provincial levels in Sibi Balochistan, Jacobabad Sindh and in various other parts of Punjab. The idea of holding a national show was first conceived during the Ayub government.

The first National Horse and Cattle Show was held in 1964 at the Fortress Stadium with Gen Azam Khan as its director assisted by Dr SM Sarwar of the animal husbandry department. The National Horse and Cattle Show has since been held in 1979, 1985, 1986, 1987, 1988, 1989, 1990, 1993, 1994 and 1995 till now.

In a documentary by a Channel British Pathe title “*Queen Elizabeth visit to Lahore 1961*” When Queen Elizabeth II and Prince Philip Duke of Edinburgh were chief guest of the event of Horse and Cattle show at Lahore, Fortress Stadium. Queen Elizabeth was presented with flowers on her arrival, as shown in Figure 3 below and was seemed to enjoy the whole event.

Figure 3 shows a charming tribute from young Pakistani to Queen Elizabeth next to her is Prince Philips

(Source: A Documentary on Queen Visit to Lahore in 1961)

Another documentary of Channel 20th Time Machine, title “*First Lady Jacqueline Kennedy and Sister Lee Radziwill Visit Pakistan (1962)*” a notable appearance was made by the First Lady of America Jacqueline Kennedy's trip to Pakistan. Princess Lee Radziwill accompanies her on 21 March 1962. She was received by President Muhammad Ayub Khan and US Ambassador Walter P. McConaughy. First Lady Jacqueline Kennedy enjoyed the horse and cattle show, she said she ‘d be looking forward to Pak American friendship. In Figure 4 below one can witness her excitement on seeing a horse.

Figure 4 First Lady Jacqueline Kennedy petting a horse in the Fortress Stadium in 1962

(Source: a documentary on Lady Jacqueline Kennedy in Pakistan)

First lady Jacqueline gives first prize in horse and cattle show to the winner in Figure 5

Figure 5 First lady Jacqueline Kennedy giving prizes during Horse and Cattle show on 21 March 1962

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

26th Chief of Air Staff (CAS) Challenge Cup, which was introduced in 1985, was accommodated at Fortress Stadium.

Fortress Stadium has always been a key venue for Horse and Cattle show along with a display of livestock, but also many spectacular feats of horsemanship, tent pegging, dressage, camel dancing, racing, folk dances, pomp, pageantry, mass-band displays and grand fireworks known as the Tattoo shows in the evening. It was accompanied by exhibition displaying Pakistani artisanship and industry (Dawn, Around town: Fortress Stadium, Lahore:

A world of entertainment, 2009). The stadium has hosted a variety of other sports, including football and field hockey, demonstrating its versatility as a sports complex (Javed, 2016). In Dawn newspaper that was published in 2003 on account of Defence Day stated that “19th Pakistan Open Squash Championship was held in Fortress Stadium where England’s top seed Peter Nicol and Canada’s World No.3 Jonathan Power were clash in the finals” (Dawn, Defence day, 2003)

In a news article of Business Records written by Zuberi, M.A in 2015, the article title was “*Nation Horse and Cattle Show ends*” states that, after 11 years, National Assembly Speaker Sardar Ayaz Sadiq and Punjab Assembly Deputy Speaker Sardar Sher Ali Gorchani attended 15th Horse and Cattle Show the event at Fortress Stadium held on March 2015. Including the playing of the anthem, performances by male and female students, a map presentation showing unity in Pakistan, and a variety of traditional dances. Ayaz Sadiq commended the participants, including the sword dances of Chatral and Khattak, and a parade of guards and soldiers. The Figure 6 below shows speaker national assembly Sadar Ayaz Sadiq standing in respect to national Anthem.

Figure 6 LAHORE: Speaker national assembly Sardar Ayaz Sadiq standing in respect of National Anthem on 4th day of 15th National Horse and Cattle Show at Fortress stadium. — INP

(Source: Business Records article)

In 2016 Army Service Sports of Pakistan (PACES) was holds in Fortress Stadium, Chief of Army Staff General Raheel Sharif was the chief guest. Army teams from China, Australia, Bahrain, Bangladesh, Indonesia, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Saudia Arabia, Maldives, Malaysia, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Turkey and England also displayed their efforts.

Fortress Stadium hosted Pakistan Leisure Leagues' football exhibition in 2017. Maj Gen Saeed-uz-Zaman Memorial Polo Cup also held in stadium. Polo players such as Hissam Ali Hyder, Alman Jalil Azam and Mir Huzaifa Ahmed and Raja Jalal Arslan, Raja Mekal Sami and Raja Sami Ullah participated in Polo Cup that held on December 26, 2018.

Figure 7 Players of Newago/Diamond Paints and Kalabagh Four vie for the ball during the Maj Gen Saeed Uz Zaman Janjua Memorial Polo Cup at the Fortress Stadium

(Source: Journal Article Business Recorder)

President General Pervez Musharraf hosted the World Cup Polo Zone “D” qualifying round with colourful ceremony opening ceremony at stadium on 13 December 2003 as Fortress Stadium main purpose is to serve as polo ground. Mian Abbas Mukhtar's superb five-wicket performance helped FG/Din Polo Team beat Master Paints/Diamond Paints 8-2½ in the Major General Saeed-uz-Zaman Memorial Polo Cup at the JS Bank Fortress Stadium on 25 January 2022.

President Dr Arif Alvi along with Chief Minister Usman Buzdar inaugurated the National Horse and Cattle Show here at Fortress Stadium. (Hasanain, 2022) The show featured a march of sports teams from different regions of Pakistan, with 85 athletes from each Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Gilgit-Baltistan, Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Sindh, and Punjab. This was followed by a cavalcade of different horse breeds, including Arabians and Highland Ponies. Additionally, a variety of cattle breeds such as Nili-Ravi and Dhani buffaloes were showcased in the event.

Figure 8 Military police personnel; perform a motor cycle stunt on the opening day of National Horse and Cattle Show at Fortress Stadium. - White Star/ M Arif

(Source: Dawn Newspaper)

4.3 Cultural Festivals Held in Fortress Stadium

Beyond sports, Lahore Fortress Stadium celebrated for its vibrant cultural festivals. The annual Pakistan Day Parade on March 23rd is one of the most significant events, commemorating the historic Lahore Resolution of 1940. This grand spectacle features military parades, cultural performances, and displays of national heritage, drawing large crowds and fostering a sense of national pride. Another key event is the Basant Festival, a traditional kite-flying celebration that marks the arrival of spring. The stadium serves as a

central gathering point for this festival, attracting thousands of participants and spectators, and highlighting the communal spirit of Lahore.

A part from all the other activities Fortress Stadium demonstrated warfare and arms display. Fly-past and army aircraft manoeuvres were the most thrilling part of Defense Day festivities at the Fortress Stadium. Arms and equipment used by infantry, armour, field artillery, air defense, signals, engineers, medical corps and EME displayed in the arms exhibition.

In 2015, the Sui Northern Executive Officers Association (SNEOA) marked International Women's Day at Fortress Stadium and congratulated SNGPL squash player Sadia Gul for winning a national award.

A reporter of Dawn news states in his article "*Lahore Garrison observes Defence Day*" that at the Fortress Stadium, visitors could enjoy a variety of military activities and display firearms, including jubilant music and aerial displays from Aviation Aircraft. Special courts were held in the units, where the message of the military commander to the troops was read. Meanwhile, the district administration organized a ceremony at the town hall in which Commodore Akbar Naqi Commandant, Naval Station, Lahore, was the chief guest. Pakistan Air Force Wing Commander Gulzar Ahmad Khan, DCO Nasim Sadiq, civil defense officials and other dignitaries also attended the ceremony.

At stadium on September 7, 2015 a flypast by Pakistan Air Force to commemorate the 1965 war. Display of tanks, big guns and other military equipment, war exercises and skills exhibited by paramilitary forces to combat terrorism. Corp Commander Gen Naveed Zaman, Ranger Punjab DG Maj Gen Umar Farooq Burki, GOC 10-Division Maj Gen Tariq Awan and Goc 11- Division Maj Gen Fida Husain were present on occasion.

Figure 9 Artillery personnel fire cannon during an event to mark the Defense Day, at Fortress Stadium in Lahore.

(Source: Dawn News)

4.4 International Delegations and State Visits

Lahore Fortress Stadium has also been a venue of choice for hosting international delegations and state dignitaries, enhancing its diplomatic significance. In 1961, Queen Elizabeth II visited the stadium during her state visit to Pakistan, where she was received with a grand ceremonial event that underscored the strong ties between Pakistan and the United Kingdom. The Figure 10 below is given by Fortress Stadium Administrative Authority that shows Queen Elizabeth shaking hands with President Ayub Khan beside him is Muhammad Ali Mala at her visit to Pakistan in 1961. Behind Queen Elizabeth is standing the Duke of Edinburgh, and General Musa Khan

Figure 10 Muhammad Ali Mala with Queen Elizabeth at the Horse and Cattle Show, Fortress Stadium Lahore 1961. Other people: Duke of Edinburgh, Governor Amir Muhammad Khan, President Ayub Khan, General Musa Khan

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

Similarly, a reporter Javed, R in his article “*Sporting venues in Pakistan: A historical perspective.*” In 2016 writes that in 1996, the stadium hosted a reception for the visiting of Chinese President Jiang Zemin, reflecting the stadium's role in fostering international relations.

Below Figure 11 is given by Fortress Stadium Administrative Authority. The images show a Foreign Dignitary to Lahore, Fortress Stadium on March 1964. Were a Foreign Dignitary is giving ways prizes along with Major general Wasi ud Din during Horse and Cattle show.

Figure 11 Foreign Dignitary giving way prizes along with Major General Wasi ud Din during Horse & Cattle Show at Fortress Stadium- March 1964

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

Another Figure 12 was given to researcher by Fortress Stadium Administrative Authority. The shows General Officer Commanding 10th division Major general Kherwaja Wasi ud Din visit Fortress Stadium during Horse and Cattle show in March 1944.

Figure 12 President Field Marshal Ayub Khan received by General Officer Commanding 10 Division Major General Kherwaja Wasi ud Din at Fortress Stadium during Horse and Cattle Show - March 1964

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

The Figure 13 below shows visit of Commander in Chief General Musa visiting Fortress Stadium to meet officers and soldiers of 10th Division in field in 1966.

Figure 13 Commander in Chief General Musa meeting with officer and soldier of 10 Division in field

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

The Shah of Iran Muhammad Rez Shah Pahlavi visited Fortress Stadium in his First Foreign visit to Pakistan in 1950. A warm relation between two countries started when they signed the friendship treaty. The Figure 14 of Shah of Iran meeting 10th Division of Pakistan was given by Fortress Stadium Administrative Authority.

Figure 14 Shah of Iran visit to Pakistan

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

In 1957 Malaysia Prince first visited Pakistan. A diplomatic relation was established between two countries. The below images are of Malaysian Prince shaking hands with the Commander of 10th Division. The Figure 15 was provided by Fortress Stadium Administrative Authority

Figure 15 Malaysian Prince during his visit to 10 Division

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

In 1962 Prime Minister of Malaysia Abdul Razak bin Hussein Al Haj visited Pakistan and held a meeting with the officers of 10th Division in January.

Figure 16 Prime Minister of Malaya (now Malaysia) Abdul Razak bin Hussein Al-Haj meeting Officer of 10 Division - January 1962

(Source: Fortress Stadium Archives)

4.5 Community Engagement in Fortress Stadium

Lahore Fortress Stadium plays a vital role in community engagement, hosting events that cater to various social causes. Charity matches, awareness campaigns, and community fairs

have utilized the stadium's expansive space to benefit the local community. These events foster a sense of unity and social responsibility, reinforcing the stadium's status as a public asset.

Stadium hold first-ever three-day international CNG exhibition at the Fortress Stadium's expo centre which was inaugurated by Chief Minister Pervaiz Elahi on December 2006. A complete range of CNG products and technology ranging from buses to motorcycles, compressors, cylinders and generators will be on display at the exhibition being organised by the Punjab transport department in collaboration with the private sector. A part from this three-day Chinese Commodities Exhibition was held on Fortress Stadium Expo Centre. Punjab Information Technology Minister Abdul Aleem Khan inaugurated this.

The 25-tonne relief was sent to Bannu from the North Waziristan Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) Relief camp at Fortress Stadium, an army relief camp on 30th June 2014.

4.6 Challenges and Adaptations of Fortress Stadium

Despite its illustrious history, Lahore Fortress Stadium has faced challenges related to maintenance and modernization. Efforts to preserve its historical essence while upgrading its facilities to meet contemporary standards have been ongoing. Renovations and infrastructural improvements have implemented to ensure the stadium remains a top-tier venue for future events, balancing heritage conservation with modern needs.

4.7 Development phases of Fortress Stadium

“Lahore Fortress Stadium was built on the idea of polo ground. The army used this stadium for polo games.” Says Secretary Manager of Fortress Stadium. “But due to growing urbanization and local population the polo ground was converted into shopping mall in

2000s.” when the researched asked him about the major development that happened in Fortress Stadium.

In an article of Dawn, “*Around town: Fortress Stadium, Lahore: A world of entertainment*” it is stated that the development of the Fortress area around the stadium has significantly boosted its popularity. There are shops, cafes and restaurants in the open areas outside the stadium, making it a business and entertainment centre. It is also one of the busiest commercial areas in Lahore. The main amenities and entertainment facilities at Lahore Fortress Stadium are:

- Fortress Square Mall
- Joy land Amusement Park
- St. John's Park
- Sindbad's Wonderland

4.8 Architectural Significant of Fortress Stadium

Conway describe meaning of architecture in his book “*Understanding architecture: An introduction to architecture and architectural history (2nd edition)*” in 2005 as architecture is an art or science of building (Conway, 2005). In current study the term architecture denotes to elevation of the building. Leland M. Roth and Amanda C. Roth Clark explains the word architectural significant in their book “*Understanding Architecture - Its Elements, History, and Meaning (3rd edit.)*” in 2018 as “A measure of the impact or importance of a building. The functional or aesthetic design of the building, and/or the methods used to construct the building can all add or detract from a building's architectural significance. In current research architectural significant represents significant of Fortress Stadium is a measure of how

important the Fortress Stadium Building is. It determines the building's design and construction.

The building of Stadium not only venue sporting events, but is also an iconic structure. The design incorporates key features such as imposing facades, intricate brickwork, and expansive seating arrangements, enhancing both its aesthetic appeal and functional efficiency. Furthermore, its architectural significance lies not only in its physical form but also in its symbolic representation of national pride and cultural identity. Studying Lahore Fortress Stadium offers valuable insights into the design innovations of the era and the cultural narratives they embody, making it a crucial subject for understanding the intersection of architecture, history, and culture in Pakistan

The Fortress Stadium is a prominent example of mid-20th century architecture that uniquely blends design elements with modern construction techniques. Built in 1960, the stadium reflects both the cultural heritage and forward-looking aspirations of Pakistan. The use of local materials in its construction demonstrates a conscious effort to root the structure in its cultural and historical context, while the modernist approach to its overall design ensures its relevance for contemporary events. The stadium's ability to host a wide range of activities, from sports to cultural festivals, displays its architectural versatility and robustness.

Following information is the overview of the Fortress Stadium with its key components. This information was provided by Secretary Manager of Fortress Stadium. The researcher then organized that information in following headings.

LAND IN FORTRESS STADIUM: Fortress Stadium comprises of approximately 166 acres.

COST OF CONSTRUCTION OF FORTRESS STADIUM: Initial cost of construction of Fortress Stadium was not figures out in available documents. Stadium was renovated and reconstructed in 1971 on a new design. Cost of project was assessed as Rupees 10.8 million. Construction of new blocks increased the cost to 17.0 million.

Table 1 Breakdown of cost analysis as under: -

Sr.	Details	Amount in millions
1.	Initial expenditure on reconstruction	Rs. 10.8
2.	Administration Block	Rs 0.9
3.	Breeder's Camp	Rs 1.0
4.	Additional accommodation	Rs 3.9
5.	Ancillary services	Rs 0.4
Grand Total		Rs 17.0

Secretary Manager of Fortress Stadium provided the cost analysis table of Fortress Stadium.

LAYOUT OF FORTRESS STADIUM: Fortress Stadium with its allied structures and green area stand prominently North of Aziz Bhatti Road and West of Shami Road in Lahore Cantonment. The main components of Stadium are main block, side block, arena with steps/terraces, green areas and metaled roads.

SEATING CAPACITY: Steps/ terraces build inside arena have the seating capacity for approximately 20,000 spectators.

4.9 ARCHITECTURAL STYLE OF FORTRESS STADIUM

The architectural style of Fortress Stadium can be summarized as a wide façade surrounded by driveways. Stadium was built in fort style with 12 different entrance gates. The wall is tall and very thick. For the decoration and ornamentation of the building, geometrical compositions are used with the blend of two-dimensional pictorial sculpture on exterior walls. The Gates of the fortress are much decorated. The used of geometrical pattern made by steel is one of the most beautiful factors. The exterior landscape of the stadium is admirable,

large gardens with small seating space and military memorabilia. These gardens are placed within rectangular wall enclosure. This part is further explained in chapter Exterior and Interior design analysis of fortress stadium.

4.10 Satellite Aerial View of Fortress Stadium

A satellite aerial view of Fortress Stadium in Figure 17 is taken from Google Earth to help researcher fully understands the layout of the stadium. The researcher was unable to get the floor plan of the stadium due to certain restriction.

Figure 17 The satellite view Fortress Stadium

(Source: Google Earth)

Satellite view is shown in the document because the floor plan could not be provided to outsiders due to administrative strictness.

CHAPTER 5

Exterior and Interior Design Analysis of Fortress Stadium

This chapter gives the detail overview of Fortress Stadium about its architectural significance, style and design influences. This part is divided into two areas, one that fully explains the exterior design including all the major and minor of Fortress Stadium. Other area explains interior design including interior layout, interior elements and changes that were made over time. A detail analysis is provided with supportive images to help understand the topic, labelled images are also given in following chapter for better understanding,

5.1 Exterior Design of Fortress Stadium

Exterior design refers to a process of planning, designing and organising the exterior elements of a building or structure. It encompasses aspects such as the façade, roofline, materials, colours and landscaping, with aim of enhancing both the aesthetic and functional qualities of the building. (Ching, 2015) (Broadbeent, 1980) (Reasmussen, 1959). In this study the exterior design of the Fortress Stadium is described according to the definition given above.

The exterior design of Fortress Stadium is simple, geometrical and rectangular in structure. The exterior design of Fortress Stadium has not change much. However, the space was utilized in one way or other by introducing entrainments spaces, mall, restaurants and play area. Fortress Stadium was constructed in late 1950s. When Field Marshal Muhammad Ayub Khan was Pakistan's President who come with formal decision of reconstruction of Fortress Stadium in 1963. Reconstruction started in 1968 and completed in 1971. After that, no prominent changes were made to the exterior of the building, except the use of additional space for public entertainment. The façade of the stadium has been in compact since then.

5.1.1 Walls of Fortress Stadium

Whitney, William Dwight and Benjamine E Smith define walls in their book *“The Century Dictionary and Encyclopaedia, Vol8”* as the walls are the support to roof, floor and ceiling that enclose a space as part of the building envelope along with a roof to give building form: and to provide shelter and security.

The exterior walls of the stadium are designed in fort style. The walls are thick and are large. The wall of Fortress Stadium has battlement. Battlements are a defensive device that forms the breastwork or the crown of the breastwork of any of the defences and is a sequence of alternating crenels and merlons. The crenels make a function of arrowlits, opened from the top, sometimes closed with movable curtains. The merlons in the battlement functions as a shield, sometimes equipped with arrowlits. The types of battlements which Fortress Stadium is Ghibellines battlement, that is, the type of crenelation, which spread in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries. Battlement was used mostly in the Middle Ages. Late, they became a decorative element. The Figure 18 below describe the battlements and its parts

Figure 18 the Image show labelling of battlement, crenels and merlons

(Source: website)

The Figure 19 below highlights the battlement on top walls of fortress stadium. During Middle Ages, the battlements were used to provide protections to defenders while being able to attack. Later, in 21st century, when the stadium was being constructed the battlements were used as decorative features that symbolize strength and protection.

Figure 19 the image shows battlement of Fortress Stadium

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

5.1.2 Gates of Fortress Stadium

Gate is a point of entry to or from a space enclosed by walls. The word derived from an old Norse “gat” meaning road or path. The concept was originally referred to the gap or hole in the wall or fence rather than a barrier which closed it. (Ethmonline, 2019)

Fortress Stadium have twelve gates, only one gate is open to outsiders to view the stadium form inside rest of eleven gates are only open during events. Each gate has its own number starting from 1 and ending at 12 that is placed right in the middle of the gate. The Gates of the fortress are much decorated. The used of geometrical composition made by steel and is one of the most beautiful factors. The gate is 14 ft height and 25 ft width. The use of different

geometric shapes such as octagon and rectangles that are repetitively used to make a composition.

Figure 20 image shows the geometric composition on gate along with arch

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 20 label above shows the arch, geometric composition and placement of gate number

On top of the gate stands four-centred arch. On the outside side of the door arch is of plan chocolate brown colour with no ornamentation. While on the other side of the gate, there are two ornaments at each corner of the arch, which is round eave end tile also called rosette. The Figure 21 below shows an enclose picture of ornament used at the inside of the stadium gate for decoration purpose. An illustration is also provided in Figure 22.

Figure 21 an enclose picture of rosette

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 22 image shows a sketch of ornament shown on image above along with a close-up picture

(Illustration made by Researcher)

5.1.3 Front Elevation of Fortress Stadium

A front elevation of fortress stadium shows the front of the building, including its entrance, windows and other design features it also the entry elevation or façade. It provides the visual impression of the building and set the tone of entire structure. The front elevation showcases fortress stadium primary features, architectural style and aesthetics.

The front elevation of Fortress Stadium reflects growing urbanization and modernization. It reflects a blend of modernist element typically of mid-20th Century. The front elevation of Fortress Stadium has clean lines, muted arches, a few ornamentations, large windows and design based on functionality. On the front one can visibly see the material used in building such as, steel, concrete, glass. The use of geometrical shapes can also be examined on front elevation of stadium.

Thought over the time the colour of the exterior changes from orange to beige to black. As shown in Figure 23 the front elevation wall of stadium was orange-brown by the end of 2012. Since the image doesn't have good resolution, the exact colour is hard to tell. The Figure 24 shows paints of front elevation were changed from orange-brown to beige and the colour was there till 2020. The Fortress Administration states when the new Secretary Manager was

appointed in 2020 the exterior walls needed a redo. So, the Secretary Manager changed the exterior paint colour from beige to dark grey as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 23 Exterior of Fortress Stadium by end of 2012

(Source website)

Figure 24 Exterior of Fortress Stadium by end on 2020

(Source Website)

Figure 25 Exterior of Fortress Stadium current 2024

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

On the front elevation of stadium there is a blend of fine lines and perfect composition. The front of stadium can be symmetrically divided vertically. there are two types of rectangles on the front elevation of stadium as seen in Figure 26.

Figure 26 image shows rectangular space after every two arches

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

One type is brought and has four-centered arches inside these rectangles. The arche inside the wide rectangle is cut through vertical and horizontal lines. These cuts create smaller rectangles inside the wide rectangle that carries an ornament. This ornament reflects \horse and cattle show (information on ornaments are given under next handing “Ornamentation on

exterior walls of Fortress Stadium”). After every two wide rectangles there is a narrow rectangle that does not have any arch but is cut both vertically and horizontally. These cut spaces have small windows in them. These windows provide ventilations in office on the inner side of stadium. The use of vertical and horizontal clean lines inside the arches have given architecture a better composition. Each line has a perfect line weight that adds beautification to the structure.

All the labelling to explain the paragraph above is done in Figure 27 below to help reader understands the point of view of researcher.

Figure 27 shows the labelling of wide rectangle and narrow rectangles

(Photograph taken by researcher)

5.1.4 Ornamentation on exterior walls of Fortress Stadium

Ornamentation is defining as two- and three-dimensional surface enrichment of a building (Merryman, 2007). In current study the term ornamentation refers to two dimensional and three-dimensional decoration of Fortress Stadium on its exterior and interior walls.

The only ornamentation that is available is on the exterior walls inside the arches as show in Figure 28 to Figure 34, which are in shapes of animals that are displayed during Horse and

Cattle show. The animals include bulls, horse, camels and goats. Apart from animals' human figure can also be witness. A circular shape is a common ornament that can be seen with each animal. The circular shape ornament is considered to be trade mark of Horse and Cattle show is one of the major events held in Fortress Stadium.

There is total eight different ornaments that are in the centre of each arch.

The Figure 28 to Figure 34 display different ornaments used on exterior wall of the stadium.

Figure 28 image shows three horses

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 28 above shows three horses that can be consider as dancing horses by how their faces are tilted and the movement of their feet. With them a circular shape is seen that is a trademark for Horse and Cattle Show.

Figure 29 image shows bulls and their calf

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 29 above shows two adult bulls and two young bulls with that can be consider as bull family consisting of two adult bulls and their two calves. With them a circular shape is seen that is a trademark for Horse and Cattle Show. This ornament is repeated twice.

Figure 30 image shows a pair of camel standing on sand

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 30 above shows a pair of camel. The camels are wearing jewels in their neck and with a saddle on their back. A saddle is a seat for a rider to sit on back of animal them. A circular shape is seen that is a trademark for Horse and Cattle Show.

Figure 31 image shows a musician with drum a man controlling a dancing camel.

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 31 above shows a dancing camel with a musician and a horse trainer. The musician is caring a drum and the training is seemed to give instruction to camel for its

dancing steps with them a circular shape is seen that is a trademark for Horse and Cattle Show.

Figure 32 image shows a human figure on horse performing tent pegging

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 32 above shows tent pegging. Tent pegging is one of the most seen sports that take place during Horse and Cattle show. It is a cavalry sport of ancient origin that has a mounted horseman riding at gallop using a lance or sword to pick up, pierce, slice or stab a small ground target or series of small ground target.

Figure 33 the images show three cows in aerial view

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 33 above shows two adult bulls and one young bull with its head face downwards. With them a circular shape is seen that is a trademark for Horse and Cattle Show.

Figure 34 the image represents a dancing horse along with musicians

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 34 above shows a dancing horse with a musician and a horse trainer. The musician is caring a duff and the training is seemed to give instruction to horse for its dancing steps. The horse is wearing traditional necklace and is beautifully decorated. With them a circular shape is seen that is a trademark for Horse and Cattle Show.

5.1.5 Free standing sculptures on roof of Fortress Stadium

Free standing sculptures on roof of fortress stadium are not attached to any other structure such as wall or building a can be viewed from all sides. these sculptures are made of metal. The base is small that is mounted on a plinth which is a small platform that act as pedestals. The sculptures are shaded with metal shade to provide protection to the sculptures from climate changes. There are four sculptures of men riding horses. Each of them different emotions such as war, conquest, victory and bravery.

The Figure 35 below is of the four sculptures.

The sculpture on very left of the image represent war, the sculpture next to it who has his sword slightly upward represent conquest, the sculpture holding Pakistan flag represent victory. The sculpture on very right holding a sword diagonal straight represent bravery.

Figure 35 sculptures on top of the stadium

(source Website)

Moreover, in collective they represent the emotions in Horse and Cattle show. Where there is a war between who is the best among them, everyone has a conquest for reaching the top, where only one is victorious and the bravery of people and animals display during the competition.

One more prominent feature about sculptures is they were not there from the beginning. They were placed after 2012 refer to Figure 36. Though the exact date isn't found when were they placed. But while researching images after 2012 shows the presence of sculptures. Only one image from a blog was found during year of 2012. The image Figure 36 is from that blog. The image below clearly shows two national flags of Pakistan are there and not the sculptures.

Figure 36 the image is from 2012

(Source Website)

The Figure 37 shows the instead of four relief horse sculpture instead of flags. These sculptures came around 2013. However, the current Fortress Administrative authority representative nor the staff members know when were they placed. No data on newspapers were found excepts the pictures after 2012 shows the arrival of these sculptures. Though they know what these sculptures represent which is mention in above paragraphs.

Figure 37 image from after 2013

(Source Website)

The Figure 37 above shows the flags have been replaced by sculptures by the 2013.

Figure 38 image taken in 2023

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 38 above shows current status of the sculptures and above them is a shade.

5.1.6 Other details of Fortress Stadium

The other details of fortress stadium are staircase and the use of available spaces for public entities.

A staircase is visible from the outside of the structure that leads to the entrance of commentary room of the stadium. It is not open to general public though. When there is an event, the commentator uses these stairs to enter the commentary room. The staircase is in middle of front elevation of the fortress stadium and right below the sculptures. At first it was visible from the front because they were covered by glass. Now it is covered with iron shields, to match the front decor. The Figure 39 below show staircase with glass coverage.

Figure 39 image when there was glass coverage.

(Source Website)

Figure 40 existing image coverage by iron shields.

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 40 above shows the staircase is covered by iron shields and is painted black.

5.1.7 Landscape and Military memorabilia of Fortress Stadium

The landscape of fortress stadium includes geophysical defined landforms such as gardens.

The gardens in fortress stadium contain shrubs, bushes and trees.

The landscape of the stadium is admirable, large gardens with small seating space and military memorabilia. These gardens are placed within rectangular wall enclosure.

There are two gardens and in between them is a two-way security check point. The gardens are also a host for military memorabilia. The military equipment which are collected for their historical significance are place in these gardens. Such items are tallest national flag, a submarine, Aircraft: Canadair CL-13B Sabre Mk.6 and a military tank

The one side of the garden has a flag pole, military air plan and submarine. On the other garden there is a tank and open space. These are actual military equipment that reflects armed forces.

Figure 41 image shows Flag pole at Fortress Stadium

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 41 above shows that tallest ever national flag of Pakistan. On 14th August 2016, the tallest ever “Nishan-e-Pakistan” (National Flag) in the country was installed on 192ft high pole at Fortress Stadium Lahore Garrison to mark the Independence Day celebration. According to ISPR, the size of the flag is 30x50 ft wide while last tallest flag was installed in Karachi with height of 185 ft. (Pakistan, 2016).

Figure 42 submarine at the garden of the Fortress Stadium

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 42 above shows a military submarine at the fortress stadium garden.

Figure 43 military airplane used by PAF

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 43 above of aircraft in the fortress stadium gardens that is Aircraft: Canadair CL-13B Sabre Mk.6, it was registration in 1970.

Figure 44 Description under the aircraft

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Translation: Airplane F- 86 is known as Sabre jet. On 6 September 1965, squad leader Muhammad Mahmood Alam (MM Alam) as GD piolet used this F-86 Sabre jet to kill the two-hunter jet of Indian army on the enemy's land. However, three fighter plans were severely damaged. On the next day 7 September 1965 on Sargodha airbase MM Alam distorted four more Hunter fighter jet. Pakistan air force granted Sitara-i-Jurat to the great hero M.M Alam on his courage and valour. This airplane of Pakistan air force will always remember the war of Pak-India, 1965 veteran and great hero M.M Alam for his excellence achievement and the completion of his incredible mission will always will be remembered.

Figure 45 the image shows the tank on the other garden

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 45 above is of military tank. The tank has its own history. The tank is there from 1962 till now. The tank is available in an old picture taken from Fortress Stadium archives.

the tank is behind Major General Khawaja Wasi ud Din, General Officer commanding 10 division with officers of 24 Cavalry Division Armour Regiment in image below. It is Sherman Tank used by 24th Calvary until 1963. In march 1964, unit got the first complement of M-48 (Patton) tanks. The Commandant took the regiment to the Armoured Fighting Vehicle Ranges in January 1963. It was a successful firing exercise and there was not a single accident during the whole exercise (Bajwa, 2013)

Figure 46 Major General Khawaja Wasi ud Din, General Officer commanding 10 division with officers of 24 Cavalry Division Armor Regiment

(Source Fortress Stadium Archives)

5.2 Interior Design of Fortress Stadium

John F. Pile in his book “Interior Design 3rd edition” explains interior design is the art and science of enhancing the interior of the building to achieve healthier and more aesthetically pleasing environment for the person using the space. In this study interior design of the fortress stadium is describe according to the definition given above.

The interior layout of stadium is positioned at 90-degree to each other and more emphasis on horizontal axis, and less on vertical axis. The material used to build interior structure are reinforced concrete and steel, along with brass ornament. A visual expression of structure is vibrant rather than hiding structural elements. The seating structure is circular with cubic

spacing. The inner structure of Fortress Stadium is in symmetrical balance or symmetrical mirror work, which can be divided vertically from centre.

Shown in Figure 47, the line cuts the inner structure vertically. that is the evidence for a symmetrical balanced structure. An inner structural elements of fortress stadium are arranged on either side of a central axis in a way that is equally weighted. This achieves visual balance on both ends of the structure.

The ornamentation in fortress stadium is done through brass relief sculptures. The inner walls of the stadium were originally painted in mud brown colour till 2000s after that the colour was changed to beige

Figure 47 inner structure cut vertically

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 48 inside view of stadium. The image shows main seating area.

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

5.2.1 Main Sitting Area of Fortress Stadium

The main sitting area of fortress stadium is also called the stadium bowl or sitting structure, which is the area where spectators view the event. The stadium bowl is a collection of individual stands. The design of stadium bowl is important for the safety of individual spectators. The sightlines of stadium sitting is designed so that that occupants of further-back seats have less of the views blocked by those further forward. The fortress stadium bowl provides a safe environment for spectators. This includes clearways for spectators to pass each other and to safely egress and evacuate in emergency.

The stadium main sitting area comprise of a three-story building, such as ground floor, first floor and commentary room, with offices only on ground and first floor. The whole structure is of bricks and concrete and contains metal railing on stairs and balcony of the first floor. A whole window wall made the commentary room to accommodate the commenter and brass and metal frames for relief sculptures.

Figure 49 label image of main seating area of Fortress Stadium

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

For better understanding the researcher have added labels in Figure 49 above. To understand the components of fortress stadium main sitting area.

5.2.2 Ground Floor of Fortress Stadium

The ground floor comprises of 38 columns, 10 steps for seating, four large seating segments in which one large segment is further divided into two small segments, with space between four small segments, the space/ gape between them is 12ft enough to park a car refer to figure 49 given below. The centre of sitting area on ground floor has a door that led to elevator to the commentary room. On the ceiling, there are eight beams support the terraces above them. Figure 50 marks the where elevator is located.

Figure 50 The are marked in the shows the elevator entrance

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 51 below shows the left side of the inner of fortress stadium. the gap label in Figure 52 shows the how the division of large sitting segment is made into two smaller sitting segments.

Figure 51 image shows large segment of ground floor seating divided into small two segments

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 52 the area marked shows the gap between two large segments

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 53 below shows the sitting steps. There are 10 sitting steps in one sitting segment,

Figure 53 10 steps for seating

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 54 eight beams to support upper terraces

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 54 above shows beams that support the first-floor terrace and sitting area. These beams are horizontal member spanning an opening and carrying load of first floor. This beam is also called lintel.

Figure 55 side view of the ground floor

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 55 above shows right side of main sitting area of fortress stadium.

5.2.3 First floor of Fortress Stadium

The First floor of fortress stadium comprises of terraces, a total of 40 columns from which 4 columns support the structure of commentary area above it which is marked in Figure 56 while the other 36 support the top beam/ roof of the stadium, nine steps for sitting, the one step is larger than the other from centre because of the stairs. To enter terraces a set of

staircases is present right next to elevator. Once first floor reached, the terraces are few steps level down. These terraces also act as a shade to ground floor sitting area.

Figure 56 label are four columns that support the commentary room

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 57 weighting columns on one side of the Main seating area

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 58 view of the stadium from first floor

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 59 nine steps for seating

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 59 above shows a closeup of sitting space on first floor. There are 9 sitting steps spectators to sit and enjoy the event.

Figure 60 two large steps are marked in image for the chief guest to seat.

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 60 label above shows two large steps for chief guest to seat and enjoy the event.

Figure 61 View of stage from the first floor

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 62 arial view of other side from the first floor

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

5.2.4 Second Floor of Fortress Stadium

The Second floor comprises of only commentary room. Four columns that rise from second floor support the commentary room are label in Figure 63. The entrance to commentary room is from two ways. One is from ground floor though elevator, the other is though staircases, which are visible from the outside of the stadium.

Figure 63 label image shows the commentary room and four columns that support it

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

This is not the only characterises of main sitting area. There was one more feature that is now not a part of stadium. A set of stairs was there till 1990s and is removed now. The stairs connected ground to first floor not from the inside of the area but from the outside. The stairs used to be on the front and in the middle of main seating area. As shown in Figure 64 below one can see UAE emperor walking down the stairs.

Figure 64 the set of stairs are were removed; UAE emperor can be seen using those stairs

(source: a documentary on Sultan Golden performing in Fortress Stadium)

5.2.5 Columns of Fortress Stadium

The columns in fortress stadium are a vertical structure that supports the weight of structure above it. The column is large and made of concrete. They are used for support, decoration and are freestanding.

There is total 78 columns in the structure design of main seating space, 38 columns are on ground floor that provide support to 8 beams to first floor, 40 are on first floor from which 36 columns provide support to roof of stadium while 4 provide support to commentary room. Each column has equally divided space between them. Each column has a LED light to provide light at night time. However, the after 2 to 4 columns two has enclose space between them, hang relief sculpture. The sculpture is as old as the structure itself so no record is kept on why were they made and how designed that. There are total of six different sculpture that are repeated again. For better understanding the research has given labels in Figure 65.

Figure 65 the label marks show enclosed space and ornamentation between them

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

5.2.6 Relief sculptures in between columns of fortress stadium.

The relief sculpture in between two columns of fortress stadium is as animal figure projection from a two-dimensional background while remaining attached to it. This sculpture is a complex art that combines elements of both two-dimensional pictorial art and three-dimensional sculpture arts. The Figure 66 to Figure 71 shows relief sculpture between the inner columns of fortress stadium

The sculpture is the depiction of different animals and birds that are part of Horse and Cattle show for which Fortress Stadium is famous. A total of 10 sculpture on ground floor and 10 on first floor. These sculptures are made with brass and have steel frame. The relief sculpture is made of brass and depict one of the performances that happens in Horse and Cattle show at Fortress Stadium

Figure 66 ornament No. 1

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

In Figure 66 above it can be assumed that it is a free hanging sculpture of a horse trying to jump over some kind of hurdle. In other words, it depicts a horse hurdle race. It represents overcoming difficulty or obstacles.

Figure 67 ornament No. 2

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

In Figure 67 above two horses can be seen and in the middle of them is a drum. The sculpture represents dancing horses, which represent greetings.

Figure 68 ornament No. 3

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

In Figure 68 above shows a bird, can be a parrot or owl sitting on the stem. This represent harmony and balance which is practiced during the performances of Horse and Cattle show.

Figure 69 ornament No. 4

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 69 above shows relief sculpture that represents tent pegging one of the most interesting sports played at Horse and Cattle show. In this sport, riders on horseback aim to knock down or pick up tent pegs using a lance or stick while galloping, often in a competitive team race format.

Figure 70 ornament No. 5

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 70 above is a relief sculpture of bullfight, in these bulls show their straight and courage to win.

Figure 71 ornament No. 6

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Figure 71 above shown, two camels. One camel face is made, middle camel is dancing and the last one is standing. However, this ornament a perfect picture is sketched of camel dance. One of the most interesting shows at Horse and Cattle show, it shows when camel enter only its face some in view, then camel perform series of dance steps and at the end it stands straight

5.2.7 Pedestal Stage on ground fortress stadium

The pedestal stage is in the centre of the inner fortress stadium as shown in figure 71. The stage is used for handing out prizes to the winners and for chief guest to view animals and pet them.

The pedestal stage is 14 ft length and 8 ft width. From the back side it has four steps and from the front it has three steps, the front side also have one small pedestal on sides of steps where flag poles can be hanged. The pedestal stage is right in the centre of the main seating area and exact on 90 degrees to it is screen. The pedestal stage has white Karaka Marble tiles. The stage gets covered with carpets during events. The stage is also the place where the prizes are distributed along where speeches are made. Figure 73 and Figure 74 shows how this stage is decorated for events.

Figure 72 Pedestal stage from back and front view

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

Figure 73 stage decorated in 1960s during the visit of Queen Elizabeth and Lady Jacqueline

(Source Journal Article)

Figure 74 stage decorated during recent Horse and Cattle 2015.

(Source Fortress Stadium Archives)

5.2.8 Screen in Ground of Fortress Stadium

This is right in front of the stage and main seating area. The screen has 26 flag poles. The flags are hanged according to the needs of the event. The screen is used to show different art work

Figure 75 the use of screen

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

5.2.9 Additional Sitting space of Fortress Stadium

The stadium has a total of 36 small segments of seating space and 16 large segment seating space. The main seating area has 8 large seating space, and on each side of main eating area there is 4 large seating space. Between two gates of stadium there is a large seating segment which is visually divided into 3 smaller segments with colour partition. The main seating area lies between 1st and 2nd gate of the stadium. 11th and 12th gates are used by the performers entrance and exit door remaining 10 gates are used for entrance. The additional seating space is shown in Figure 76

Figure 76 Additional sitting space from left and right side. Large segment is visually divided into parts.

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The additional seating space has 16 seating steps, this space used to have shades in 1960s till 1987 as shown in Figure 77 to Figure 79, after that no such record was found, after 2003 the shades were removed and then after Covid-19 the shades were used again in 2022 but currently these are no shades. That can be seen in Figure 81.

Figure 77 use of shade in 1960s

(Source: A documentary)

Figure 78 use of shades in 1987

(Source: A documentary)

Figure 79 presence of shades 1990s

(Source: A documentary)

Figure 80 in 2015 only few seatings area has shades

(Source: Dawb Newspaper)

Figure 81 Currently 2024 pillars for shades that are not constructed so far

(Photograph taken by Researcher)

The Researcher Develop Questions on The Bases of The Objective

The questions were developed by the researcher on bases of objective. The Administrative Authority of Fortress Stadium was interviewed on bases of these questions. The answers given by administrative representative helped the researcher in identifying key elements for thesis.

1. Can you describe the key architectural features of Fortress Stadium that distinguish it from other stadiums in the region?

"Fortress Stadium is known for its blend of modern and traditional architectural elements. The use of robust materials like brick and concrete, combined with intricate detailing. The stadium's open layout and large entrance arches are particularly distinctive.

2. How the design of the stadium evolved over time, and what has been the major factors driving these changes?

"The design has evolved primarily in response to the growing demands of the city and the need to accommodate a wider variety of events. Originally built with a focus on sports especially polo games and horse and cattle show. The stadium has since expanded its facilities to host cultural and commercial events."

3. What were the original design intentions behind the stadium's layout, and how do they align with the current usage of the space?

"The original design was intended to create a multifunctional space that could serve both sports and community events. The layout was designed to allow for large crowds, with an emphasis on clear sightlines and ease of movement. Over time, we've maintained these principles while adapting to modern requirements."

4. Can you explain any significant renovations or modifications that have been made to the interior design of the stadium?

"Significant renovations have included upgrading the seating areas, enhancing lighting, and improving acoustics to better support large-scale events."

5. What challenges have you faced in maintaining the architectural integrity of the stadium while accommodating modern needs?

"One of the biggest challenges has been balancing the need for modernization with preserving the stadium's historic architecture. We've approached this by carefully planning renovations that respect the original design while incorporating new technologies and materials that enhance functionality."

6. How does the interior design of the stadium cater to different types of events and activities held here?

"The interior design is quite flexible, allowing us to reconfigure spaces for different types of events, whether it's a sports match, a concert, or a cultural festival."

7. What future plans, if any, are there for further architectural or interior design developments at Fortress Stadium?

"We do have plans for further developments, including expanding seating capacity, and possibly introducing more sustainable design features like solar panels. However, any future changes will be carefully considered to maintain the stadium's architectural integrity."

CHAPTER 6

Conclusion & Future Recommendation

Conclusion

The conclusion of this research highlights the enduring architectural and cultural significance of Fortress Stadium in Lahore. Through a qualitative analysis, the study has demonstrated how the stadium serves as a functional sports venue, reflecting both historical influences and contemporary needs. The insights gathered from interviews, observations, and archival research underscore the careful balance maintained between preserving the stadium's original design and accommodating modern requirements. As Lahore continues to evolve, Fortress Stadium remains a vital landmark, embodying the dynamic intersection of tradition and progress within the urban landscape. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of how architectural spaces can influence and reflect the cultural identity of a city, offering valuable perspectives for future urban development and heritage conservation efforts.

Future Recommendations

For further study, it is recommended to explore the following areas:

A comparative study between Fortress Stadium and other historical stadiums in Pakistan or South Asia could provide deeper insights into regional architectural trends and cultural influences. Explore sustainable practices in the maintenance and renovation of heritage buildings like Fortress Stadium, focusing on energy efficiency, resource conservation, and the use of eco-friendly materials. Conduct a study on the ongoing debate between preservation of historical architecture and the need for urban development, using Fortress Stadium as a case study to explore potential compromises and solutions.

Analyse the impact of government policies and regulations on the conservation and management of Fortress Stadium, identifying areas where policy improvements could support better preservation efforts. A longitudinal study could be conducted to track the architectural evolution of Fortress Stadium over the next few decades, providing insights into how heritage buildings adapt to future urban and cultural shifts.

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